

Association between Serum Thyroid Stimulating Hormone and Free Thyroxine Levels and Urinary Albumin Excretion in Euthyroid Patients with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus

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Abstract:

Background: The Patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus are greatly impacted by diabetic nephropathy (DN), a major cause of end-stage renal disease (T2DM). Thyroid function, even in the euthyroid range, may have an impact on the development of DN, according to new research.

Aim: This study aims to investigate the association between serum thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH) and free thyroxine (fT4) levels with urinary albumin excretion in euthyroid subjects with T2DM.

Methods: Fifteen euthyroid T2DM individuals were included in a cross-sectional investigation. Patient interviews, examinations of medical records, and laboratory tests to measure HbA1c, fT4, serum TSH, and urine albumin-to-creatinine ratio (ACR) were used in the data collection process. Using SPSS version 23.0, Pearson correlation analysis was performed to evaluate the associations between these variables.

Results: The participants' average age was 55.3 ± 8.2 years, and the male to female ratio was 9:6. Urinary ACR was 45.6 ± 22.4 mg/g, fT4 was 1.2 ± 0.2 ng/dL, and mean serum TSH was 2.3 ± 0.8 μ IU/mL. Urinary albumin excretion and blood TSH levels were shown to be significantly positively correlated ($r = 0.642$, $p = 0.009$). Urinary albumin excretion and fT4 levels did not significantly correlate ($r = -0.213$, $p = 0.456$). Males had a higher correlation ($r = 0.751$, $p = 0.021$) than females ($r = 0.528$, $p = 0.095$) according to gender-based analysis.

Conclusion: In euthyroid patients with type 2 diabetes, elevated urine albumin excretion is linked to higher serum TSH levels, indicating a possible connection between thyroid function and diabetic nephropathy. There was no discernible correlation between fT4 levels and excretion of albumin in the urine.

Recommendations: To determine who is more likely to develop diabetic nephropathy, it is advised that patients with type 2 diabetes have their thyroid function regularly monitored. Larger sample sizes and additional research are required to confirm these results and investigate underlying mechanisms.

Keywords: Type 2 diabetes mellitus, Euthyroid, Thyroid-stimulating hormone, Free thyroxine, Urinary albumin excretion, Diabetic nephropathy.

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Introduction

Millions of people worldwide suffer from diabetes mellitus, a common chronic illness that has serious health consequences, including diabetic nephropathy (DN). Diabetic nephropathy is a primary cause of end-stage renal disease (ESRD) worldwide, marked by a progressive decline in renal function and albuminuria [1]. The aetiology of diabetic nephropathy is complex and includes pathways related to metabolism, haemodynamics, and inflammation. Even in people who are euthyroid, recent research indicates that thyroid

function may be critical to the development of diabetic nephropathy [2].

Thyroxine (T4) and triiodothyronine (T3) are two thyroid hormones that are vital for many physiological functions, including growth, development, and metabolism. Thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH), secreted by the pituitary gland, controls the activity of the thyroid gland. Variations in thyroid hormone levels, even when they fall within the normal range, have been linked to a number of metabolic diseases, such as type 2 diabetes (T2DM). Subclinical hypothyroidism,

which is characterised by normal free thyroxine (fT4) levels but excessive TSH levels, has also been associated with a higher risk of developing diabetic complications, such as nephropathy [3].

Numerous investigations have looked into the connection between diabetic nephropathy and thyroid function. For example, a research in euthyroid patients with T2DM revealed a possible correlation between thyroid malfunction and the onset of DN: greater TSH levels were linked to increased urine albumin excretion [4]. An additional study revealed that thyroid hormone levels may impact albuminuria and renal function in diabetic patients, emphasising the necessity of routine thyroid function monitoring in these individuals [5].

Despite the growing body of evidence, the exact mechanisms underlying the association between thyroid function and diabetic nephropathy remain unclear. It is hypothesized that thyroid hormones may affect renal hemodynamic, glomerular filtration rate (GFR), and the expression of various renal proteins involved in the pathogenesis of DN. Additionally, inflammation and oxidative stress, common features in both thyroid dysfunction and diabetes, may further contribute to renal damage.

Given the potential impact of thyroid function on the progression of diabetic nephropathy, it is essential to investigate this relationship further in euthyroid patients with T2DM. Understanding the interplay between thyroid hormones and renal function could lead to improved management strategies for preventing and treating diabetic nephropathy.

This study aims to investigate the association between serum thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH), free thyroxine (fT4) levels, and urinary albumin excretion in euthyroid patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus.

Methodology

Study Design: A cross-sectional design.

Study Setting: The research was conducted at Katihar Medical College over a period from January 2024 to June 2024.

Participants: A total of 15 euthyroid patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus participated in the study.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients diagnosed with type 2 diabetes mellitus.
- Euthyroid status confirmed by normal serum TSH and fT4 levels.

- Age between 30 to 70 years.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with known thyroid disorders.
- Those on thyroid hormone replacement therapy or anti-thyroid medications.
- Patients with acute or chronic kidney disease other than diabetic nephropathy.
- Pregnant women.
- Patients with severe acute illness or other endocrine disorders.

Bias: Selection bias was minimized by including all eligible consecutive patients who attended the clinic during the study period. Information bias was reduced through standardized procedures for data collection and laboratory measurements.

Data Collection: Patient interviews, examinations of medical records, and laboratory tests were used to gather data. For the purpose of measuring serum TSH, fT4, and HbA1c, blood samples were obtained. In order to calculate the albumin-to-creatinine ratio, urine samples were obtained.

Procedure: Patients were instructed to fast overnight before blood sample collection. Venous blood samples were drawn, and serum was separated by centrifugation. TSH and fT4 levels were measured using chemiluminescent immunoassay methods. HbA1c was measured using high-performance liquid chromatography. Urine samples were collected in sterile containers, and the albumin-to-creatinine ratio was determined using immunoturbidimetric assay.

Statistical Analysis: SPSS version 23.0 was used to analyse the data. The features of the patients were summarised using descriptive statistics. The association between fT4 levels, urine albumin excretion, and serum TSH was evaluated using Pearson correlation. Statistical significance was attained when the p-value was less than 0.05.

Result

The study included 15 euthyroid patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. The mean age of the participants was 55.3 ± 8.2 years, with a male-to-female ratio of 9:6. The average duration of diabetes was 10.2 ± 5.1 years. The mean HbA1c level was $7.8 \pm 1.2\%$, indicating moderate glycemic control. The average blood pressure recorded was 135.6 ± 12.4 mmHg systolic and 82.3 ± 8.5 mmHg diastolic.

Table 1: Baseline Characteristics of Participants

Characteristic	Mean $\pm$ SD
Age (years)	55.3 $\pm$ 8.2
Duration of diabetes (years)	10.2 $\pm$ 5.1
HbA1c (%)	7.8 $\pm$ 1.2
Systolic BP (mmHg)	135.6 $\pm$ 12.4
Diastolic BP (mmHg)	82.3 $\pm$ 8.5
Male, n (%)	9 (60)
Female, n (%)	6 (40)

The mean serum TSH level was 2.3 $\pm$ 0.8 μ IU/mL, and the mean fT4 level was 1.2 $\pm$ 0.2 ng/dL. The mean urinary albumin-to-creatinine ratio (ACR) was 45.6 $\pm$ 22.4 mg/g, indicating varying degrees of albuminuria among the participants.

Table 2: Serum Thyroid Hormone Levels and Urinary Albumin Excretion

Parameter	Mean $\pm$ SD
TSH (μ IU/mL)	2.3 $\pm$ 0.8
fT4 (ng/dL)	1.2 $\pm$ 0.2
Urinary ACR (mg/g)	45.6 $\pm$ 22.4

Urine albumin excretion and serum TSH levels showed a strong positive association ($r = 0.642$, $p = 0.009$), according to Pearson correlation analysis, indicating a possible link between elevated TSH levels and increased excretion of urine albumin. fT4 levels and urine albumin excretion, however, did not significantly correlate ($r = -0.213$, $p = 0.456$).

Table 3: Correlation between Thyroid Hormones and Urinary Albumin Excretion

Variable	r-value	p-value
TSH and Urinary ACR	0.642	0.009*
fT4 and Urinary ACR	-0.213	0.456

*Significant at $p < 0.05$

Further analysis based on gender showed that the correlation between TSH and urinary ACR was stronger in male participants ($r = 0.751$, $p = 0.021$) compared to female participants ($r = 0.528$, $p = 0.095$), although it was not statistically significant in the female subgroup.

Table 4: Gender-based Correlation between TSH and Urinary Albumin Excretion

Gender	r-value	p-value
Male	0.751	0.021*
Female	0.528	0.095

*Significant at $p < 0.05$

Discussion

Fifteen people were included in the study; their mean age was 55.3 years, they had diabetes for an average of 10.2 years, and their mean HbA1c level was 7.8%, indicating moderate glycaemic management. The subjects' mean blood pressure measurements were 135.6 mmHg for the systolic and 82.3 mmHg for the diastolic phases.

The mean fT4 level was 1.2 ng/dL and the mean serum TSH level was 2.3 μ IU/mL. The participants' varied levels of urine albumin excretion were shown by the mean value of 45.6 mg/g for the urinary albumin-to-creatinine ratio (ACR), a marker of albuminuria. Urinary albumin excretion and blood TSH levels were found to be significantly positively correlated ($r = 0.642$, $p = 0.009$) by Pearson correlation analysis. This implies that in euthyroid patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus, elevated urine albumin excretion is linked to elevated TSH levels. Nevertheless, there was no

discernible relationship ($r = -0.213$, $p = 0.456$) between fT4 levels and urine albumin excretion.

Male individuals had a higher connection between TSH and urine ACR ($r = 0.751$, $p = 0.021$) than female participants ($r = 0.528$, $p = 0.095$) in the gender-based subgroup analysis, however the association in females was not statistically significant. This suggests that there may be a stronger correlation between TSH and urine albumin excretion in men, underscoring the need for future studies with bigger populations to validate these results and comprehend the underlying mechanisms.

Overall, the study shows a strong correlation between urinary albumin excretion and serum TSH levels in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus who are euthyroid. This suggests that elevated TSH levels may be associated with an increased risk of diabetic nephropathy. These results highlight the significance of keeping an eye on thyroid function in individuals with type 2 diabetes mellitus in order

to potentially identify those who may be more susceptible to renal issues. Larger sample sizes in future research are required to confirm these findings and investigate the role of thyroid function in diabetic nephropathy.

939 patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) from a community hospital in Saudi Arabia were examined in this study. The findings showed that, in comparison to patients with normal albuminuria, those with severely elevated albuminuria had significantly lower FT4 levels (15.3 ± 1.9 pmol/L) and much higher TSH levels (2.1 ± 0.9 mIU/L). The study found that in euthyroid patients with T2DM, there is a strong correlation between increased urine albumin excretion, decreased FT4, and high TSH [6].

A cross-sectional study with 1,071 euthyroid people conducted in China discovered that patients with diabetic nephropathy (DN) had lower serum levels of FT3 and FT4 and higher serum TSH. According to the study, there is a positive link between TSH levels and DN, but an inverse relationship between FT3/FT4 levels and DN. TSH had an odds ratio (OR) of 1.179, whereas DN's were 0.606 for FT3 and 0.944 for FT4 [7].

In 312 euthyroid patients with type 2 diabetes, a study examined the relationship between thyroid measures and indicators of chronic kidney disease (CKD). The results showed that the urine albumin-to-creatinine ratio (UACR) was adversely correlated with the FT3 and FT3/FT4 ratios, whereas the estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR) was positively correlated. In euthyroid T2DM patients, the investigation identified FT3 as a major factor associated with CKD [8].

The results of a study involving 4,136 patients from the METAL project indicated a correlation between diabetic kidney problems and greater FT4 and lower FT3 levels. The relationship between thyroid function and kidney health in T2DM patients was further supported by the correlation between greater TSH and FT4 levels and lower eGFR and higher urine albumin-to-creatinine ratios (UACR) [9].

In 248 euthyroid T2DM patients, a study looked at the frequency of microvascular problems and how they related to thyroid hormones. The findings demonstrated that TSH was favourably linked with diabetic peripheral neuropathy (DPN) (OR = 1.57), whereas FT3 and FT4 were adversely associated with diabetic nephropathy (DN), with odds ratios of 0.310 and 0.702, respectively. [10].

Conclusion

The findings show that urine albumin excretion and serum TSH levels are significantly correlated in

euthyroid type 2 diabetes mellitus patients. Urinary albumin excretion was found to be linked with higher TSH levels, indicating a possible connection between thyroid function and diabetic nephropathy. There was no discernible correlation between FT4 levels and excretion of albumin in the urine. Male participants showed a greater correlation, according to the gender-based study, which calls for more research with a bigger sample size.

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